

Fishing Architecture

Natural Zigzags Artificial Rocks Alice Nouvet^a

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Drawings as Objects of Knowledge

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The curves and zigzags of the drawing are lumpy due to the unevenness of the blotting paper and the different reliefs of the cutting grooves. What are rocks? What is sand? Is that an egg in the centre of the composition? More, is that a giant worm emerging from the contour lines? In view of this, is it urban planning or an abstract composition? The engraving represents “a 200’ sand pile which will be continuously detonated from within for landslides” printed in a 1960s journal at the forefront of environmental concerns.

The drawing DM2004, “Project for a Park”, resonates with other endless representations of nature within the Drawing Matter collection. Trees, water, mountains, rocks, natural elements in contrast or dialogue with the shapes of human construction. Inquiring the ambiguity of architectural drawings aims to engage us to rethink the breadth of lives, of lives and deaths, considered in our worlds. Rather than detaching and representing with detail the things that inhabit the pile of sand, the drawing conveys an entangled world. Hence, this object has a strong resonance today, as Marielle Macé wrote in *Une pluie d’oiseau*, “a strange time where [ecosystems], which are disappearing, come back: come back into our field of vision, our attention, our speech. (...) As if we were trying to hear [and see] them better (to hear [and see] them at last) at the very moment they are leaving.” How can architectural drawing forge new forms of connection and understanding with the elusive realm of nature?

Figure 1 — Keith Albarn, Ian Knight, Anthony Hutt, *Journal of Centre for Environmental Studies*, 1967. Courtesy Drawing Matter, 2004.

The call launched by the KU Leuven school of architecture suggested to go through Drawing Matter's architectural representation archive and to re-enact, re-draw or re-read some of the drawings to activate the idea of circularity within the archive.

This was an opportunity to take Fishing Architecture's questions on representation (for instance, how can architectural representation be useful to scientific purposes) and to connect them to the Drawing Matter's archives.

By choosing three drawings, our aim was to (1) set the problem: the lack of representation of the sea's depths, (2) find within the drawings ways of representing the sea (tools, format, scale that could be to our advantage), (3) re-draw or re-enact one of them as an attempt to entangle the history of the drawing —by whom and for what outcome was it drawn?—, to a piece of the sea's history — the cod of Newfoundland's Grand Banks in the 1990s. In other words, connect two different histories and geographies.

A panorama [Figure 1], dating from 1630, imagining the reconstruction of the naval theatre of Rome, somehow triggered the idea of lack of representation of the sea's depths. After going through the catalogue of Drawing Matter's archives, that was the first depiction of the sea in the center of a drawing. But still, it's a smooth surface that represents the sea, ignoring the life that inhabits it. Around the smooth surface, a very detailed city drawn from a bird's eye view. The structure of the city raises the question: the buildings do not follow the same vanishing point. Moreover, some buildings seem to have been drawn on another piece of paper and added afterwards; the stroke's quality being different, one could assume that the buildings are not drawn by the same person. This technical aspect is to look at carefully: thanks to a collage, different geographies and narratives have been brought together within one frame.

An imprint dating from 1967 [Figure 2] and published in a journal of environmental concern among poems that brought forward for consideration the idea of abstraction. The unevenness of the paper and the irregular cutting grooves resulted in lumpy curves and zigzags. What are rocks? Is this an egg? Is it an urban plan or an abstract composition? Rather than detaching and representing with details the things that inhabits the pile of sand, the drawing conveys an entangled world. In other words, rather than representing static topographic lines the drawing plays with the imagination of the mind and somehow renders visible the movement of forms of life.

It's an urban plan (undated) of an idealised capital city in Italy [Figure 3], projected within the frame of an engineering school exercise, that invited us to re-enact its history. The sinusoidal river lead to open water. Here again, the sea is represented as a continuous even surface. Therefore, as an exercise too, we tried to draw the symmetry of the urban plan, a kind of diptych that would represent the water's spaces. The first attempt raised many questions: which scale to render visible? Which fish's story to tell? [Figure 4]

In the second attempt, we tried to connect the history of the urban plan with the history of the Newfoundland's cod in the 1990s. To narrate the different episodes through which the cod went through, we used tracing paper and layered them together. The first tracing paper shows the state of affairs: the cod is disappearing (blue cod), its morphologic size is changing [Figure 5]. The second one narrates that because cod disappears [Figure 6], the trophic chain is going through some perturbations: the biomass of the cod preys increase (red fish). The prey happens to eat the cod larvae and eggs and zooplankton (oblique hatching), therefore diminishing even more their biomass. The decrease of the zooplankton (dashed oblique hatching) results in the increase of phytoplankton's biomass (red hatching). The latter often leads to an algae bloom [Figure 7].

One has to note that this assemblage between species is not a reality fixed once and for all. An ecological assemblage results from permanent interaction between species and changes with seasons and the environment. Therefore, it is very difficult to grasp what is actually happening. The livings will always take us by surprise.

Interacting with three drawings in three different ways raised questions: how can architectural drawing forge new forms of connections and understandings with the elusive realm of nature? How can architectural representation grasp the permanent change of lifecycles? What are the most compelling drawings in Drawing Matters collections that could help us to tackle this problem?

Figure 2 — Contoured topographical plan of an idealized capital city, Italy. Courtesy Drawing Matter, undated.

Figure 3 — A cod story. Decrease of zooplankton, increase of Phytoplankton.

Figure 4 — A cod story. Cod disappearing (in blue), cod's prey biomass increasing (in red).

Figure 5 — Symetrical view. Who inhabits the sea?

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